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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research work was to develop innovative environmental friendly building brick and study their performance, particularly on wetting and drying cycle. To understand the relative significance of these results geopolymer building brick with which different $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ has been manufactured. Geopolymer building brick has been manufactured by using highly alkaline solution and an aluminosilicate source. During this research work, (230 × 110 × 75 mm) size building bricks were manufactured. After 25 days of atmospheric curing, the bricks attained a crushing strength of 10 to 12 Mpa. Then the bricks were submerged in water to observe the effect of wetting and drying cycle on strength of brick. Results comprised that even after 10th cycle, there is no specific deterioration in the crushing strength of brick.

Keywords: Fly ash, geopolymer, wetting drying cycle & atmospheric curing.

INTRODUCTION

The traditional building bricks are mostly manufactured by using soil and clay as raw materials. So, use of wastes as raw materials for the production of ceramic building products not only conserves energy, but also helps in pollution control and adds a solution to the waste disposal problem (Scarano et al. 1998; Garg et al. 1996; Kumar, 2002; Kumar, 2003). Earlier research has shown that it is possible to use 100% fly ash as the binder in mortar by activating them with an alkali activator, such as; caustic alkalis, silicate salts, and non silicate salts of weak acids (Bakharev et al. 1999a; Talling & Brandstetr, 1989). During the last decade, considerable research efforts have been directed towards the development of inorganic geopolymers, due to the wide range of potential applications for these materials. Several reports can be found in the literature on the synthesis, properties and applications of geopolymers (Stevenson and Sagoe-Crentsil, 2005).

Geopolymerization is a geosynthesis (reaction that chemically integrates minerals) that depends on the ability of the aluminium ion (6-fold or 4-fold coordination) to induce crystallographical and chemical changes in a silica backbone (Davidovits, 2005). It is observed that fly ash, one of the possible sources for making geopolymer binders, is available abundantly worldwide, and yet its usage till date is very limited (Hardjito et al; 2004). The wide variety of potential applications of geopolymer includes: fire resistant materials, thermal insulation, low-tech building materials, low energy ceramic tiles, refractory items, cements and concretes (Davidovits 2008). The most important factor is to develop a cost effective energy efficient process for manufacture of fly ash building brick by using geopolymerization process. Therefore, this research work is focused on a specific property i.e. effect of wetting drying cycle on strength of geopolymer fly ash building brick manufactured by atmospheric curing.

METHODOLOGY**Preparation of geopolymerization activator**

The process of geopolymerization requires alkaline chemical activator for initiation of reaction in formation of mineral polymer structures. This chemical activator has been synthetically prepared by taking commercial grade sodium hydroxide in pellet form with water, in the presence of alkaline base chemicals consisting of anions of O^{2-} , $[\text{OH}]^{1-}$, Cl^{1-} and $[\text{SO}_4]^{2-}$ in different concentrations (Nayak et al., 2009) and sodium silicate solution. The pH of chemical activator

is maintained within 11-11.5 for suitable geopolymerization reaction. The concentration of anion group chemicals in the activator is maintained depending on the chemical constitution of the oxides and silicates of aluminum, calcium, magnesium, iron bearing mineral phases which is needed for effective reaction. The concentration of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 with respect to alkali (Na_2O) in the fly ash mix governs the geopolymerization reaction.

Casting and curing of brick

In the current research work, fly ash the burnt mineral residue of pulverized coal of thermal power plant was used as raw material. It is a compound of silica, alumina, and also contains minor amounts of other oxides such as Fe, Na, Ca, Mg, and K, etc. Alumina and silica are the major chemical constituents of fly ash which exist in the form of quartz (SiO_2) and mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) mineral phases. The chemical analysis of fly ash carried out by XRF is given in Table-1. Fly ash with a suitable weight proportion of alkaline activator has mixed in a pan mixer in presence of the alkaline activator and water. Then the wet mixtures are used for casting of $230 \times 110 \times 75$ mm size building brick by 20 ton compaction pressure. The cast products are cured under normal atmospheric condition (35°C). The principle of geopolymerization has been adopted by making different mix designs of fly ash where the reaction of fly ash with alkaline activator takes place mainly with silica and alumino-silicates. The principle of geopolymerization has been adopted by making different mix designs of fly ash where the reaction of fly ash with alkaline activator takes place mainly with silica and alumino-silicates. The manufacturing process of geopolymer fly ash building brick has been designed as: weighing of raw material, preparation of chemical activator, mixing, casting and demoulding followed by curing (Muduli et al 2013). The concentration of anion group chemicals in the activator is maintained depending on the chemical constitution of the oxides and silicates of aluminum, calcium, magnesium, iron bearing mineral phases which is needed for effective reaction. The concentration of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 with respect to alkali (Na_2O) in the fly ash mix governs the geopolymerization reaction. Ratio of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ of different mixtures of alkaline activator and fly ash is given in Table-2. Here, we discuss the properties of fly ash building brick after 10th cycle of wetting and drying.

Table – 1: Chemical analysis of fly ash

Constituent %	Na_2O	MgO	PO_2O_5	SO_3	CaO	Al_2O_3	SiO_2	TiO_2	Cr_2O_3	Fe_2O_3
Fly ash	0.09	0.285	0.51	0.14	0.47	35.5	59.5	0.94	0.01	2.01

Table – 2: Raw material mix design and crushing strength of building brick

Raw material (wt. %)	Mix-1 (K1)	Mix-2 (K2)	Mix-3 (K3)	Mix – 4 (K4)	Mix – 5 (K5)
Fly ash	87	87	87	87	87
Activator solution	4	5	6	7	8
Water	9	8	7	6	5
$\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$	0.025	0.038	0.052	0.065	0.078
Days	Crushing strength (Mpa)				
5	2	4	4	8	12
10	4	5.5	8	14	21
15	5	6.5	15	23	34
20	6	7	21	31	41
25	6.5	8	24	37	48

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Geopolymer reaction is dependent on temperature. The hardening of fly ash mix in the presence of alkaline activator generally takes a longer duration to attend the desired strength. Therefore, conditions of curing are the major aspects to develop a high quality geopolymer product. The bricks made out of different mix are cured by exposing to the air temperature at 35°C up to 25 days for the build-up of strength. Table-2 shows the build-up of strength of the bricks of different mix compositions at atmospheric curing of 35°C temperature. It is observed that with the increase in alkaline activator and $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{SiO}_2)$ ratio, the strength of fly ash product gradually increases. The fly ash mix consisting

of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio above 0.038 shows a remarkable increase in the strength. The findings on development of strength indicates that alkaline activator consisting of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} is effective at atmospheric temperature of 35°C . The substantial increase of strength of fly ash mix is due to the increase of alkali concentration and formation of alkaline alumino-silicate phases. The X-ray diffraction data as shown in Figure -1 shows the intensity corresponding to alkaline alumino-silicate phases in different fly ash mix. The sample K0 represents the fly ash used in preparation of different mix with alkaline activator (base material). The XRD data shows analcime, sodalite, cancrinite, natrolite, herschelite, and mullite, as predominant mineral phases. During curing, minerals of silica in the form of quartz and alumino-silicate in the form of mullite reacts with alkali activator. The reaction proceeds through gradual dissolution of silica and alumina depending upon the concentration of alkali. With increase of alkali concentration (from K1 to K5), the formation of alkali alumino-silicates have increased due to dissolution of quartz and mullite phases present in the fly ash. The formation of alkali alumino-silicates is distinct in the fly ash mix K3, K4 and K5 as seen from the XRD data. The other mineral phases are mostly hydrous alkali alumino-silicates which resembles analcime sodalite, cancrinite natrolite and herschelite minerals. The formation of these phases is expected due to different substitution of H_2O , Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions.

The electron micrograph of a fully reacted solidified fly ash product obtained from K5 mixture is shown in Figure- 2. The micrograph shows the formation of crystalline structures of sodium assisted cross-linked alumino-silicate geopolymer phases. These alkaline phases occur in acicular form and seem to have cross-linked into a matrix in the solidified product. The elemental distribution of crystalline phases of acicular structure of solidified fly ash product shows the presence of Na, Al, and Si, which corresponds to the geopolymer phase of sodium aluminum silicate. The micrograph also shows that the reaction of fly ash in alkaline activator consisting of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} form crystalline grains of sodium aluminum silicates. These grains of sodium aluminum silicates with minor to trace

amounts of Fe, Ti, S, Mg, Ca, and K are mostly fibrous and elongated. These mineral phases with different cation and anion substitution grow into amorphous to crystalline structures by dissolution and solidification. Inter-ordination of the polymerized minerals helps in the build-up of the cementation property. Depending upon the bonding strength, the geopolymerisation process is flexible to make high strength building materials such as bricks ranging in crushing strength from 7 to 12 MPa.

Effect of wetting and drying cyclic condition on brick property

By implementing geopolymer process fly ash building bricks has been manufactured by maintaining $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio 0.025 to 0.038. The fly ash building bricks of size 230×110×75 mm produced by hydraulic compaction after 25 days of atmospheric curing weigh in the range of 2.80 to 3.20 kg after 8 to 11% of water absorption and attain up to 10 MPa crushing strength. To observe the durability behavior of fly ash brick, experiment has been carried out on wetting and drying cycle. The cyclic test of wetting and drying are carried out for 70days determine the water absorption and crushing strength of the bricks. The mix design maintaining $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio 0.025 has been used to observe the wetting and drying cyclic effect on strength of fly ash geopolymer building brick (Figure- 1a.). During the study total 30 numbers of bricks are used in the experimental trials for continuous wetting and drying cycle. All the bricks are immersed in water and dried at 65°C in hot air oven for 24 hours during the cyclic test. For each cycle 3 bricks are taken out in every one week interval after wetting and drying to measure dry and wet weight and the crushing strength. At a time all the bricks undergo continuous wetting and drying in the cycle test. The cyclic test has been carried out up to 10th stage. The results of dry weight, water absorption and crushing strength has been given in the Table -3. From the experimental condition it is observed that the water soaked weight of the brick varies from 3.00kg to 3.60kg and the dry weight varies within 2.50kg to 3.10kg with water absorption of 10-29%. The crushing strength of the geopolymer fly ash building brick ranges from 5.12 to 8.27Mpa. There is no remarkable degradation in the strength of brick. The results indicate that the crushing strength during the cyclic tests (1st cycle to 10th cycle) varies within 6.71 to 7.63Mpa (figure 1 b.).

Table – 3: Wetting drying cyclic effect of geopolymer fly ash brick.

Cyclic no.	Water soaked weight	Dry weight	Water absorption (%)	Crushing strength (Mpa)
1 st Cycle	3.200	2.800	14	6.83
	3.500	3.000	16	6.71
	3.250	2.850	14	7.28
2 nd Cycle	3.300	3.000	10	7.93
	3.350	3.000	12	6.88
	3.250	2.900	12	8.27
3 rd Cycle	3.000	2.500	20	5.90
	3.250	2.800	16	6.90
	3.250	2.900	12	7.65
4 th Cycle	3.350	3.050	10	8.05
	3.100	2.750	13	7.95
	3.600	3.100	16	6.92
5 th Cycle	3.050	2.600	15	7.56
	3.250	2.750	15	7.40
	3.450	3.000	13	6.91
6 th Cycle	3.150	2.750	13	6.96
	3.300	2.800	15	8.0
	3.350	2.900	13	7.35
7 th Cycle	3.350	2.800	20	5.38
	3.250	2.600	25	5.82
	3.250	2.750	18	6.40
8 th Cycle	3.300	2.900	14	7.29
	3.100	2.600	19	7.63
	3.400	2.950	15	8.51
9 th Cycle	3.350	3.150	6	5.30
	3.100	2.850	9	5.12
	3.150	2.900	9	6.77
10 th Cycle	3.300	2.550	29	6.93
	3.100	2.750	13	7.45
	3.400	2.700	26	7.63

In geopolymerization process SO_4^{2-} is an effective ion of higher hydration energy which promotes hydration of silicates, aluminates and alkalis and enhances the interactions of monomers in formation of crystalline phases (Wang et al., 2006 ; Desbats-Le and Frizon, 2011). The Cl^- ion acts as an accelerator in gel formation and helps in crystallization (Lee and Van Deventer, 2002; Desbats-Le and Frizon, 2011). In this process, the silica and alumina bearing minerals of fly ash react with the soluble alkalis at ambient temperature to form the geopolymer minerals in presence of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} . Chemical reactions between oxide phases of silica and alumina under alkaline condition form OH bearing sodium-aluminium-silicate structures which on solidification develops the binding strength. The dissolution of Al and Si from fly ash occurs in the presence of Sodium hydroxide, and also the optimum reaction takes place in the presence of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions in atmospheric temperature to form a compact and strong structure. So, even after 10^{th} cycle of wetting and drying, there is no remarkable change in the crushing strength of the brick.

CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that by using the Geopolymerization process, building bricks can be made for commercial exploitation using fly ash. The reaction process of geopolymerization depends on the type of raw materials and on the concentration of alkaline activator. The sodium based alkaline activator (pH > 11.5) consisting of anions of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} is the most effective one to inhibit the reaction process and help in attaining the desired strength in atmospheric curing. The compressive strength increases with the increase of $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3+\text{SiO}_2)$ ratio, which is dependent on concentration of NaOH. It is also observed that by putting the bricks in water for 70 days there is no more change in the strength and appearance of the bricks. We have found that the geopolymerization process is a green technology which aims for 100% utilization of waste materials.

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